

Table S1. Dental wear stages vs ontogenetic ages in years.

Dental wear stages	Ontogenetic ages		
	From	To	Mean
I	0	1.5	0.75
II	1.5	3	2.5
III	3	4	3.5
IV	4	8	6
V	8	12	10
VI	12	16	14
VII	16	20	18
VIII	20	24	22
IX	24	27	25.5